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“GLOBAL RAQAMLI INTEGRATSIYALASHUV:
2030-YILGACHA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHDA
TEXNOLOGIK VA INDUSTRIAL SANOATNI RIVOJLANTIRISH
ORQALI MIKRO VA MAKROIQTISODIY BARQAROR
O'SISHNI TA'MINLASH DOLZARBLIGI”

“GLOBAL DIGITAL INTEGRATION: THE RELEVANCE OF
ENSURING MICRO AND MACROECONOMIC SUSTAINABLE
GROWTH THROUGH TECHNOLOGICAL AND INDUSTRIAL
DEVELOPMENT IN THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN
ECONOMY BY 2030”

«ГЛОБАЛЬНАЯ ЦИФРОВАЯ ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ:
АКТУАЛЬНОСТЬ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО
МИКРО- И МАКРОЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА ЧЕРЕЗ
РАЗВИТИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ И ИНДУСТРИАЛЬНОЙ
ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ В ПЕРЕХОДЕ К ЗЕЛЁНОЙ
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- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
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- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
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- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
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- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
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- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
- 08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
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- 08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
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- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF PRODUCTION COMPETITIVENESS IN TEXTILE ENTERPRISES AND THE ECONOMIC MECHANISMS OF ITS FORMATION

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Abstract. This thesis analyzes the current state of production competitiveness in textile enterprises and examines the elements of the economic mechanism that shape and influence it. The study investigates the impact of product quality, labor productivity, production costs, investment activity, innovation, and management efficiency on enterprise competitiveness. The main factors contributing to competitive advantages in the textile industry are identified, and recommendations aimed at improving production efficiency are proposed. The research findings can contribute to strengthening the competitive position of textile enterprises in both domestic and international markets.

Keywords: textile enterprises, production competitiveness, economic mechanism, labor productivity, investments, innovations, product quality, production efficiency.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur tezisda to'qimachilik korxonalarida ishlab chiqarish raqobatbardoshligining hozirgi holati hamda uni shakllantiruvchi iqtisodiy mexanizm elementlari tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotda mahsulot sifati, mehnat unumdorligi, ishlab chiqarish xarajatlari, investitsion faoliyat, innovatsiyalar va boshqaruv samaradorligining korxonalar raqobatbardoshligiga ta'siri o'rganilgan. Shuningdek, to'qimachilik tarmog'ida raqobat ustunliklarini shakllantirishning asosiy omillari aniqlanib, ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirishga qaratilgan taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari korxonalarning ichki va tashqi bozorlardagi raqobat pozitsiyalarini mustahkamlashga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: to'qimachilik korxonalar, ishlab chiqarish raqobatbardoshligi, iqtisodiy mexanizm, mehnat unumdorligi, investitsiyalar, innovatsiyalar, mahsulot sifati, ishlab chiqarish samaradorligi.

Аннотация. В данном тезисе проанализировано современное состояние производственной конкурентоспособности текстильных предприятий и рассмотрены элементы экономического механизма, формирующие её развитие. В ходе исследования изучено влияние качества продукции, производительности труда, производственных затрат, инвестиционной активности, инноваций и эффективности управления на конкурентоспособность предприятий. Определены основные факторы формирования конкурентных преимуществ в текстильной отрасли и разработаны предложения по повышению эффективности производства. Результаты исследования могут способствовать укреплению конкурентных позиций текстильных предприятий на внутреннем и внешнем рынках.

Ключевые слова: текстильные предприятия, производственная конкурентоспособность, экономический механизм, производительность труда, инвестиции, инновации, качество продукции, эффективность производства.

INTRODUCTION

The acceleration of globalization processes in the world economy and the intensification of competition in international markets require manufacturing enterprises to continuously improve their competitiveness. In particular, the textile industry, as one of the important sectors of the national economy, plays a significant role in increasing export potential, creating new jobs, and expanding industrial production.

In recent years, large-scale reforms have been carried out in Uzbekistan to modernize the textile industry, attract investment, improve product quality, and expand the production of finished goods with higher added value. However, in order to secure a stable position in international markets and increase export volumes, it is necessary to further strengthen the production competitiveness of enterprises.

At present, the practice of assessing production competitiveness in the textile sector is mainly based on output volume and export indicators. The growth of production volumes or the increase in export revenues is often accepted as the main criterion for the development of the sector, while competitiveness is frequently equated with these final performance indicators. However, such an approach does not reveal which economic factors form competitive advantages in the sector, to what extent production efficiency is ensured, or how sustainable these results are. As a result, competitiveness may appear to exist externally, while its internal economic foundations may remain insufficiently developed.

Practical analysis shows that production results in the textile sector are often assessed without sufficient connection to resource-use efficiency, the depth of processing, and the technological structure of production. Despite instability in raw material supply, high energy intensity, the aging of fixed assets, and the slow growth of labor productivity, production volumes may increase in certain periods. Under such conditions, competitiveness takes the form of a temporary state and may weaken rapidly when external market conditions change. Therefore, assessment based only on output volume and export results does not reflect the real economic condition of the sector's competitiveness.

Another important aspect of the problem is that the system of indicators used at the sectoral level has been formed in a fragmented manner. Some indicators reflect resource consumption, others describe output volume, while others represent financial indicators, but no single logical relationship has been established among them. This limits the possibility of comprehensively assessing the competitiveness of the sector and makes it difficult to compare analytical results and identify dynamic changes. Most importantly, economic decisions made on the basis of these indicators are directed not toward sustainably increasing competitiveness, but toward maintaining short-term results.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Production competitiveness in the textile sector is determined not only by the volume of resources or financial results, but also by how production processes are organized and on what technical basis they are carried out. In practice, notable differences in performance among enterprises operating with the same raw materials and under similar market conditions arise mainly due to organizational and technical factors. Therefore, there is a need to quantitatively assess the technological state of the production process and the level of its management.

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